

Function Implementation of Village Consultative Agency in Sendangan Satu Sonder District Minahasa Regency

Maikel Paulbers Mawei¹, Lexi Lumingkewas², Goinpeace Tumbel³

¹Student of State Administration Master Program, Manado State University, Indonesia

^{2,3}Lecturer of State Administration Study Program, Faculty of Social Sciences, Manado State University, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine the implementation of the function of the Consultative Agency (BPD) in Sendangan 1 Village, Sonder District, Minahasa Regency, this study uses qualitative research methods. The results of the existing research indicate that: 1) Implementors in the village of Sendangan Satu do not yet know in detail the process of discussing and determining the draft village regulations following applicable regulations. 2) The draft village regulations that have been discussed and agreed to date have not yet been established as village regulations. 3) The community's aspirations have been accommodated by the BPD but not all of the community's aspirations have been followed up. 4) The place of implementation of the distribution of public aspirations is not following regulations because it is still carried out flexibly. 5) BPD and Government Officials do not know specifically the stages in the process of channelling public aspirations. 6) The supervision carried out by the BPD on the performance of the Village Head has not been thoroughly implemented. Three factors hinder the implementation of the BPD function in Sendangan 1 Village, namely standards and objectives, communication, and also the disposition of the implementer. For the advice given, implementers should understand in detail the process of discussing and agreeing on draft regulations that are following regulations, draft village regulations must be immediately set into Village Regulations by implementers so that this policy can run properly and correctly, and supervision of the performance of the Village Head must further improve.

KEYWORDS: Function, BPD, Village Government

I. INTRODUCTION

Law No. 6 of 2014 concerning Villages, illustrates that the village as an autonomous region is given special rights, including those related to village financial management, village head elections and the village development process. Villages have original autonomy rights based on customary law, can determine the composition of the government, regulate and manage their households based on their potential to achieve village development and have wealth and assets. (Undang-undang (UU) tentang Desa, 2014).

Although the village in the organizational structure of the regional government occupies the lowest place, the village is an important part to place hope in the implementation of government, development and community affairs. Therefore, it is necessary to hold coordinate within the village government to achieve the overall development goals. To achieve success in governance, development and society, it must be supported by strong collaboration from various parties, namely the Village Government, existing institutions such as the Village Consultative Agency but also the participation of the village community itself.

The Village Consultative Agency (BPD) or what is called by another name is an institution that carries out government functions whose members are representatives of the village population-based on regional representation and are determined democratically. To improve institutional performance at the village level, strengthen togetherness and increase community participation and empowerment, the village government and the Village Consultative Agency facilitate the implementation of village deliberations. The election of BPD members is carried out democratically, namely elected from and by villagers who meet the requirements of prospective BPD members.

The enactment of Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages and their derivative regulations has opened up opportunities as well as challenges for the administration of village governance in Indonesia. The presence of this law is in line with the current Nawacita concept of Mr President Jokowi, namely building from the periphery of what is meant by building from the village. Of course, village development can run optimally if it maximizes the functions of the Village Consultative Body.

The derivative of Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages which details the function of the Village Consultative Agency is Permendagri No. 110 of 2016 which contains the Functions of the Village Consultative Agency which can be formulated as

Function Implementation of Village Consultative Agency in Sendangan Satu Sonder District Minahasa Regency

follows: 1) Discussing and agreeing on the Draft Village Regulation with the Village Head; 2) Accommodate and channel the aspirations of the village community; 3) Supervise the performance of the village head. To carry out this function, BPD members have the right to submit proposals for draft Village Regulations, ask questions to the Village Government, submit proposals and/or opinions, vote and be elected and receive allowances from the Village Budget and Expenditures. (Peraturan Menteri Dalam Negeri tentang Badan Permusyawaratan Desa, 2016).

Regarding the function of the BPD in discussing and agreeing on the draft Village Regulation with the Village Head, the BPD and the Village Head essentially have the same position when there are important matters in the administration of government, development and society in the village that need to be contained and stipulated in village regulations.

Likewise, with the function of the BPD in accommodating the aspirations and channelling the aspirations of the village community, this BPD should be a place for the community to complain and convey various ideas and concrete ideas for the progress of the village itself, so that the BPD can be analogized as a parent who is ready to hear the complaints of a child who want to make something the best. Although in reality, not all public complaints are positive, sometimes people's complaints are based on personal desires that are personal for their interests.

What is not important in the function of the BPD is to monitor the performance of the Village Head, in this case, the BPD can act as a teacher who gives value to the performance of the Village Head. As a BPD teacher, he can give a warning to the Village Head if the expected performance is not appropriate or deviates from the applicable laws and regulations, moreover, the Village Head's performance leads to legal violations that can be processed legally based on existing legal evidence.

According to the research that has been carried out by Rico Masuara, namely the implementation of the function of the Village Consultative Agency (BPD) in the administration of Village Government (a study in Bolangitang Satu Village, Bolangitang Barat District, North Bolangangmongondow Regency) in the conclusion that the implementation of the functions of the Village Consultative Agency is still weak, it can even be said that it is not able to influence on improving the work of the sub-district government, in this case, the function to absorb and accommodate the aspirations that develop in the village community is still not functioning (Masuara, 2014).

When looking at the efforts of the Village Consultative Agency in carrying out its functions in the village of Sendangan Satu, Sonder District, as the results of the research that the researchers have done, it was found that there are still weaknesses in the BPD in carrying out its functions, among others, first, the Implementor in the village of Sendangan Satu still does not know in detail the discussion process. and agreeing on the draft of village regulations according to the policy, even though they do not even know the specifics of the regulations and stages in the process of channelling community aspirations. The draft village regulations that have been discussed and agreed to date have not yet been established as village regulations. The supervision carried out by the BPD on the performance of the Village Head has not been thoroughly implemented. Furthermore, the socialization given to the leaders and members of the BPD regarding the regulations governing the BPD was not optimal, then it was not too transparent in conveying the Draft Village Regulations that had been produced to the community.

Based on the description above, the researchers researched the Implementation of the Functions of the Consultative Agency in Sendangan Satu Village, Sonder District, Minahasa Regency.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Public Policy

Public Policy according to the dictionary of public administration (Chandler & Plano, 1988, p. 129) is the strategic use of existing resources to solve public or government problems. Meanwhile, according to (Easton, 1988, p. 29) implies the allocation of values by force (legitimate) to all members of society. Edwards III and Sharkansky (Islamy, 1984, p. 18) also argued that public policy is what the government says and does or does not do, policy is a set of goals and objectives of government programs.

As for James. E Anderson defines policy as the behaviour of a number of actors (officials, groups, agencies, governments) or a series of actors in a particular field of activity (Indiahono, 2009, p. 17). While Hogwood and Gunn state that there are 10 policy terms in a modern sense, namely: as a label for a field of activity, as an expression of general goals or expected state activities, as a specific proposal, as a government decision, as a formal authorization, as a program, as an output, as an "outcome", as a theory and a model, as a process.

Another definition of policy according to Thomas R. Dye, states that policy is the government's choice to determine steps to 'do' or 'not to do' (to do or not to do). (Lubis, 2007, p. 6). Meanwhile, according to Carl J. Friedrich policy is a series of concepts of action proposed by a person or group of people or government in a certain environment by specifying obstacles and opportunities, for the implementation of these proposals to achieve certain goals. Carl also details what are the main points in a policy, namely the existence of goals (goals), goals (objectives), and will (purpose). (Lubis, 2007, p. 7). Meanwhile, Nugroho said that public policy comes with a specific purpose, namely to regulate life together as stated above to achieve the agreed goals (mission and vision). (Nugroho, 2011, p. 142).

Thomas R. Dye defines public policy as whatever governments choose to do or not to do, meaning that whatever the government does or does not take action, he argues that if the government chooses to do something, it means that there must be a

Function Implementation of Village Consultative Agency in Sendangan Satu Sonder District Minahasa Regency

purpose. Or it is often interpreted as the movement or silence of the government for a purpose. (Lubis, 2007, p. 6). Frederickson defines public policy as a series of actions proposed by a group or government in a certain environment by showing obstacles and agreements against the implementation of policy proposals to achieve certain goals (Frederickson, 1997).

Steven Petterson has another opinion that public policy is a government activity carried out to overcome the problems that exist in the community. Public policy is matters relating to what the government should do regarding the problems faced from this opinion, it can be seen that the policy here is more directed at the duties and obligations of the government to issue a policy. (Tangkilisan, 2007, p. 42). According to William Dunn in (Tumbel, 2021, p. 71), the stages of public policy are: Agenda Formulation, Policy Formulation, Policy Adoption, Policy Implementation, and Policy Evaluation

Policy Implementation

Policy implementation is a complex activity with so many factors that affect the success of policy implementation. In reviewing the implementation of public policies, Edwards III asks a basic question, namely what are the prerequisites for the implementation of a policy and what are the main factors inhibiting the success of policy implementation.

In line with this thought, there is also the opinion of Donald Van Mater and Carl Van Horn in (Winarno, 2002, p. 109) which states that policy implementation is an activity in the process that includes various actions, both carried out by the government and community groups that are directed to achieve the goals and objectives that have been set. The description of the implementation of public policies above is understood as the result of thoughts that cannot be understood by the policy implementers. Policy implementation is a stage where the policies that have been determined are implemented by administrative units through the movement of existing resources with all their abilities.

Many factors also influence policymakers or the policy itself, and each member or organization cannot guarantee to avoid the risk of failure to implement public policy. By Abdul Wahab (Lumingkewas, 2006, p. 117) It is argued that the risk of failure to implement public policy can be traced to three areas:

(1) Improper policy implementation (bad execution); Improper policy implementation is also known as implementation failure. Abdul Wahab in (Lumingkewas, 2006, p. 117). In practice it is usually caused by incapable resources to implement the policy, the deficiency is generally due to a lack of insight into knowledge, skills and work experience. Although basically, the policy is good, in practice in the field it is not good because the situation and conditions in the field are less affordable, for example in remote areas or even in agencies that have a very wide working area, and the role of the surrounding community has not been supportive, resulting in the policy not being implemented properly.

(2) Poor policy (bad policy); Bad policies according to Abdul Wahab (in Lumingkewas, 2006: 118), are also called policy failures, such failures are more due to the lack of knowledge and understanding skills of policymakers on what the public needs in the field. Lack of information support is one of the causes. Such policies often have to be revised or deleted according to the latest demands that arise during fieldwork. Policymakers often make policies not based on the needs of a situation.

(3) disadvantaged policies; less fortunate Policies, usually run conditionally and tend not to last long. As stated by Islamy (Lumingkewas, 2006, p. 119) that public policymakers and implementers must be equipped with skills that will be used to better analyze, predict and predict and convince the consequences of each alternative policy they choose.

Tofler (Lumingkewas, 2006, p. 119) reminds us that the future as terra incognita, which is an area that is not recognized and supported by the statement of Robert Heilbroner said that: the future or tomorrow can only be imagined and cannot be ascertained and predicted, the future can only be effectively controlled through the real power of the present day. The capabilities and expertise that are assisted by modern technology will not guarantee to see and give certainty about what will happen in the future. This is very important for public policymakers to pay attention to.

Factors Inhibiting Policy Implementation

To see the barriers to the effectiveness of a policy, it can be seen by using the public policy process model. There are so many models in the policy implementation process that can be used. namely starting from the policy implementation model proposed by Donald Van Mater and Carl Van Horn in (Winarno, 2002, p. 110), in which they propose six variables that form the bond between policy and achievement of results as well as the importance of implementation procedures taking into account the concepts of change, control and compliance activities. Among them:

- Standard policies and targets to be achieved
- Resource
- Communication or quality of organizational reciprocity
- Characteristics of the agents involved in the implementation
- Economic, social and political environment
- Disposition or response from implementor

The model shows how the relationship between various variables, although conceptually using a partial explanation, the views in this model can be used by implementors in manipulating the improvement of public services carried out. By basing on the theory of Van Mater and Van Horn (Winarno, 2002, pp. 109-110), it can be identified that the implementation process of the

Function Implementation of Village Consultative Agency in Sendangan Satu Sonder District Minahasa Regency

Village Consultative Body's policy on the Implementation of Sendangan Satu Village Government in Sonder District, Minahasa Regency will be determined by: standard and objectives, resources, communication between organizations/implementation activities, disposition of implementation, characteristics of implementers / bureaucratic structure and social, economic and political conditions. The six variables in question are:

a. Standards and goals

In every public policy, standards and objectives must always be clearly stated in each program because with clear standards and policy objectives, it will be easier to implement policies. On the other hand, there will often be failures caused by the lack of clarity about the standards and objectives of the policy. Determination of standards and objectives, one of which can use a statement from policymakers such as through a regulation, program guidelines and evaluation criteria for a policy.

b. Resource

Resources are no less important than standards and goals. Policy resources must also be available to facilitate the implementation of a policy. Lack of or limited resources, funds and other incentives in policy implementation is the biggest contribution to the failure of policy implementation. Because no matter how clear and consistent the provisions and rules are and however accurate they are in conveying these rules, if the implementers of the policy lack the resources to do effective work, the implementation of the policy will also not be effective. These resources include:

- Staff who have the right number of skills and abilities for the job they are doing.
- Funds to finance operations
- Relevant and sufficient information on how to implement a policy.
- The authority to guarantee and ensure that the policies implemented are as desired.
- Facilities used for operationalization for the implementation of a policy.

c. Communication

For a public policy to be implemented effectively, the standards and objectives must be communicated to the implementers. This communication must be consistent and uniform (consistency and uniformity) from various sources of information. If there is no clarity and uniformity towards a standard and the objectives of a policy, it will be difficult to achieve the objectives of the policy. If different communication sources provide inconsistent (inconsistent) against a standard and objectives or sources of information provide conflicting interpretations (conflicting) then the policy will be difficult to implement intensively. The prospect of effective policy implementation is largely determined by the clarity of policy standards and objectives that are communicated to policy implementers accurately and consistently.

d. Characteristics of implementing/bureaucratic structure

Even if there are sufficient resources to implement a policy and implementers understand what and how to do it and have the will to do it, policy implementation may still be ineffective because of the inefficiency of the bureaucratic structure. This bureaucratic structure includes aspects such as organizational structure, division of authority, relationships between organizational units within the organization concerned and outside the organization and so on. Therefore, the bureaucratic structure includes the dimensions of fragmentation and standard operating procedures. The fragmentation dimension emphasizes that a fragmented bureaucratic structure can increase the failure of communication where policy implementers will have a great opportunity. This bureaucratic fragmentation will limit the ability of top officials to coordinate all relevant resources within a given jurisdiction, resulting in further inefficiency and waste of scarce resources. In other words, the successful implementation of public policy requires good cooperation from many people in the organization. The next dimension is standard operating procedures which will facilitate and uniform the actions of policy implementers in carrying out what is their field of duty.

e. Social, economic and political conditions

Another factor that has a strong influence on the model of public policy implementation is a factor outside the implementing organization itself which has a strong relationship with the implementing organization. Such as social factors, economic conditions, and political conditions surrounding the policy implementing organization.

f. Implementing disposition

Disposition in policy implementation is defined as a tendency, desire or agreement of the implementers (implementors). To implement a policy, if it is to succeed effectively and efficiently, implementers not only know what to do and have the ability to implement the policy, but they must also have the will to implement the policy. However, how the implementers exercise their discretion depends on their inclination towards a policy. Then their attitude will be influenced by their views on a policy and the way they see the influence of the policy on the interests of their organization and their interests.

(Akib, 2012, pp. 16–17) discusses the Mazmanian and Sabatier policy implementation models which are classified into three general categories. The first category is the independent aspect concerning the ease or difficulty of controlling a problem. The scopes are 1) technical difficulties, 2) behavioural diversity of the target group, 3) the percentage of the target group compared to the total population, and 4) the scope of the desired behaviour change. The second category is the intervening aspect, namely the ability of the policy to systematize the policy implementation process or policy program management. The scopes are 1) clarity and consistency of policy objectives, 2) allocation of funding sources, 3) hierarchical integration within and between

Function Implementation of Village Consultative Agency in Sendangan Satu Sonder District Minahasa Regency

implementing agencies, 4) decision rules from implementing agencies, 5) recruitment of implementing officials, and 6) formal access to external parties. The third category is the dependent aspect, namely aspects outside the policy that affect the policy implementation process. The scopes are: 1) socio-economic and technological conditions, 2) public support, 3) group attitudes and resources, 4) support from superior officials, and 5) commitment and leadership ability to implement officials. While the bound aspects shown through the stages in the implementation process include: 1) implementing agency policy outputs, 2) the willingness of the target group to comply with policy outputs, 3) the real impact of policy outputs, 4) the perceived impact of policy outputs, and 5) improvements.

The Hogwood and Gunn model propose eight conditions for implementing the policy as follows: 1) guarantee that external conditions outside the organization will not cause major problems, 2) the availability of sufficient resources, 3) the integration of the necessary resources, 4) implementation the policy is based on a reliable causal relationship, 5) causality of the relationship, 6) low dependence on other aspects, 7) the quality of understanding and commitment of the parties and 8) the correct detailing and sequencing of tasks.

III. METHODS

Interviews were conducted by gaining strong intimacy by continuing to follow what Benny and Hughes said to appreciate the value of interviews as a data collection tool (Pangkey & Sendouw, 2020, p. 2128). researchers establish close emotional relationships and intimacy with all stakeholders who were met during the study can receive a positive response and got deeper and more accurate information (Polii, 2021, p. 4).

Data analysis is an effort to systematically search and organize records of observations, interviews and documentation to increase the researcher's understanding of the findings based on the problems studied. Data analysis by Patton (Moleong, 1994, p. 103) is the process of organizing data affairs, organizing into one pattern, category and the basic unit of measure. In qualitative research, data analysis is carried out continuously until the preparation of research reports. The report should be an analytical and descriptive presentation of data that has been systematically collected and interpreted (Furchan, 1992, p. 233).

Miles and Huberman said that the data obtained from the field were analyzed through the following stages:

- The first stage is categorizing and reducing data, namely collecting all important information related to this research problem, then the data is grouped according to the topic of the problem.
- The second stage, the grouped data is then arranged in the form of narratives so that the data is in the form of a series of meaningful information according to the research problem.
- The third stage, interpreting the data by interpreting what has been given and interpreted by the informant to the problem under study.
- The fourth stage, drawing conclusions based on the narrative structure that has been prepared in the third stage so that it can provide answers to research problems.
- The fifth stage is to verify the results of data analysis with informants based on the conclusions of the fourth stage. This is intended to avoid misinterpretation of the results of interviews with several research informants that can obscure the real issue from the focus of the research (Miles & Huberman, 1992, p. 16).

While the conclusion is drawn after all the data obtained to answer the research problem, then concluded by the researcher according to the relevant theory. The conclusion of the research is a brief statement about the results of descriptive analysis and a discussion of the results of research that has been done previously. The conclusion contains the answers to the questions posed in the problem formulation.

To determine the validity of the data in qualitative research, it must meet several requirements as stated by (Lincoln & Guba, 1985), (Moleong, 1994, p. 5) in examining the data using four criteria, namely:

1. Degree of Trust (Credibility)

The application of the concept of the degree of confidence criteria is intended as a substitute for the concept of internal validity from non-qualitative research. This criterion serves to: Carry out the inquiry in such a way so that the level of confidence in the findings can be achieved. Demonstrating the degree of trustworthiness of the findings by way of proof by the researcher on the multiple facts being studied. Several ways that need to be pursued so that research results can be trusted, Nasution (1988:14) include:

- (1) Continuous observation. With continuous observation, researchers can pay attention to things more carefully, especially those related to the focus of research
- (2) Collecting reference materials. As a reference material to increase the trust and validity of the data, the results of the tape recorder or documentation materials can be used.
- (3) Hold member checks. At the end of the interview, the researcher will do a member check or re-check the outline of various things that have been conveyed by the informant based on field notes with the intention that the information obtained and used in writing research reports is following what was intended by the informant.

Function Implementation of Village Consultative Agency in Sendangan Satu Sonder District Minahasa Regency

2. Transferability

Transferability as an empirical problem depends on the similarity of the context of the sender and receiver. To carry out the transfer, the researcher tries to find and collect empirical data on events in the same context, thus the researcher is responsible for providing sufficient descriptive data. In this case, the researcher tries to provide a detailed description of how the research results can be achieved, whether the research results can be applied, will be left to the readers or users. If the user sees that in this research there is something suitable for the situation at hand, it is possible to have an involvement, although it can be assumed that no two situations are the same so that it still needs to be resolved according to their respective circumstances.

3. Dependability and Confirmability

Dependence according to conventional terms is called reliability. Reliability is a requirement for validity, only with reliable tools can valid data be obtained. The main tool of this research is the researcher himself and his supervisor, therefore to ensure the dependence and certainty of the research, what needs to be done is to combine the criteria of dependence with certainty utilizing an "audit trail" (checking and tracking a truth).

Result and Discussion
Research results with a focus on Implementation of the Functions of the Village Consultative Agency in Sendangan Satu Village, Sonder District, Minahasa Regency.

Findings of indicators Discussion and Agreement on Draft Village Regulations:

1. Implementors in Sendangan Satu Village, even more specifically the BPD, still do not know in detail the process of discussing and agreeing on the draft village regulation according to the policy.
2. Not all people have been invited to the village meeting.
3. Draft village regulations that have been discussed and agreed upon, have not yet been established as village regulations,
4. The BPD has held deliberations regarding the draft village regulation.
5. The implementors of the discussion and agreement on the Draft Village Regulation are the BPD and the Village Government.
6. The implementors in Sendangan Satu Village still do not understand in detail the timeframe in the draft village regulation proposed by the Village Head.

Findings of indicators for Accommodating and Distributing Village Community Aspirations:

1. The community's aspirations have been accommodated by the BPD but not all of the community's aspirations have been heard.
2. There is a screening process for community aspirations carried out by the BPD.
3. The place for the distribution of community aspirations is not following regulations because it is still carried out flexibly.
4. BPD and Government Officials do not know specifically the stages in the process of channelling public aspirations.

Findings of the Village Head Performance Monitoring Implementation indicators:

1. BPD has carried out supervision on the performance of the Village head but the supervision carried out has not been comprehensive.
2. The process of implementing the supervision carried out by the BPD is still not properly known by the implementor.
3. The implementor has not correctly understood the form of supervision that should be carried out by the BPD regarding the performance of the Village Head.

Research results with a focus on Inhibiting Factors in the Implementation of the Functions of the Village Consultative Agency in Sendangan Satu Village, Sonder District, Minahasa Regency.

Findings of Standard and Objective indicators:

1. The implementors still do not know the regulations related to the Village Consultative Agency (BPD).
2. The existing government officials still do not understand in detail the functions of the BPD.
3. Draft Village Regulations that have been produced to date have not yet been established as Village Regulations.
4. To date, there is no technical guidance regarding the function of the BPD from the village, sub-district or district government

Communication indicator findings:

1. The form of coordination between the BPD and the village government has been going well.
2. There is socialization given to the leadership and members of the BPD regarding the regulations governing BPD but it is not yet optimal.
3. There is a rejection from the community regarding the draft village regulations that have been produced.
4. There is an indifferent attitude regarding the input given by the community to the Village Government and BPD.

Findings of Implementing Disposition indicators:

1. The attitude of the BPD in discussing and agreeing on the draft village regulation together with the village government has been conveyed well.
2. The BPD and the Village Government have not been very transparent in conveying the Draft Village Regulations that have been produced to the Community.
3. The evaluation carried out by the BPD on the performance of the village head is still carried out in oral form, not in writing.

Function Implementation of Village Consultative Agency in Sendangan Satu Sonder District Minahasa Regency

Implementation of the Functions of the Village Consultative Agency in Sendangan Satu Village, Sonder District, Minahasa Regency

Conceptually, public policy can be seen from the Chandler and Plano public administration dictionary which says that public policy is a strategic use of existing resources to solve public or government problems. Meanwhile, according to David Easton, the notion of public policy implies the forced (legitimate) allocation of values to all members of society.

Edwards III and Sharkansky explain that public policy is what the government says and does or does not do, policy is a set of goals and objectives of government programs. Etymologically implementation comes from English "to implement" which means implementation and application. Pressman and Wildavsky formulate that providing the means to do something. According to him, the word implementation in addition to the verb must also have an object, namely policy. So basically implementation is carrying out something in this case is a policy that can have an impact on whether or not a policy is achieved by using the means to implement the policy.

As for James. E Anderson (Anderson, 2003) defines policy as the behaviour of several actors (officials, groups, agencies, governments) or a series of actors in a particular field of activity. While Hogwood and Gunn state that there are 10 policy terms in a modern sense, namely: as a label for a field of activity, as an expression of general goals or expected state activities, as a specific proposal, as a government decision, as a formal authorization, as a program, as an output, as an "outcome", as a theory and a model, as a process. Policy according to Thomas R. Dye, he states that policy is the government's choice to determine steps to 'do' or 'not to do (to do or not to do). Meanwhile, according to Carl J. Friedrich policy is a series of concepts of action proposed by a person or group of people or government in a certain environment by specifying obstacles and opportunities, for the implementation of these proposals to achieve certain goals. Carl also details what are the main points in a policy, namely the existence of goals (goals), goals (objectives), and will (purpose). The implementation of public policies emphasizes good actions taken by the government or individuals, groups or private parties that are directed to achieve the goals that have been set in the policy decisions. Policy implementation is also to measure the success or failure of a policy that is implemented in the field by the implementors and its impact on the community or its stakeholders.

In line with this thought, there is also the opinion of Donald Van Mater and Carl Van Horn in Winarno which states that policy implementation is an activity in a process that includes various actions, both carried out by the government and community groups that are directed to achieve the goals and objectives that have been set. The description of the implementation of public policies above is understood as the result of thoughts that cannot be understood by the policy implementers. Policy implementation is a stage where the policies that have been determined are implemented by administrative units through the movement of existing resources with all their abilities.

Many factors also influence the policymakers or the policy itself, and each member or organization cannot guarantee to avoid the risk of failure to implement public policy. Abdulwahab argued that the risk of failure to implement public policy can be traced to three areas:

First, the implementation of policies that are not good (bad execution); Improper policy implementation is also known as implementation failure. Abdul Wahhab. In practice it is usually caused by incapable resources to implement the policy, the deficiency is generally due to a lack of insight into knowledge, skills and work experience. Although basically, the policy is good, in practice in the field it is not good because the situation and conditions in the field are less affordable, for example in remote areas or even in agencies that have a very wide working area, and the role of the surrounding community has not been supportive, resulting in the policy not being implemented properly.

Second, the policy is not good (bad policy); According to Abdul Wahab, bad policies are also called policy failures. Such failures are more due to the lack of knowledge and skills of policymakers to understand what the public needs in the field. Lack of information support is one of the causes. Such policies often have to be revised or deleted according to the latest demands that arise during fieldwork. Policymakers often make policies not based on the needs of a situation.

Third, disadvantaged policies; less fortunate Policies, usually run conditionally and tend not to last long. As stated by Islamy that the makers and implementers of public policies must be equipped with the skills that will be used to better analyze, predict and predict and convince the consequences of each alternative policy they choose.

The policy of the Village Consultative Agency is a policy that was born from Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages as well as Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government which was then followed up by Government Regulation Number 43 of 2014 concerning Implementing Regulations of Law Number 6 the Year 2014 concerning Villages. . In the Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs Number 110 of 2016 concerning the Village Consultative Body, Article 31 explains that the BPD has the functions of: a) discussing and agreeing on the Draft Village Regulation with the Village Head; b) accommodate and channel the aspirations of the Village community; and c) supervise the performance of the Village Head.

Article 44 concerning Discussion and Agreement on Draft Village Regulations explains (1) BPD and the Village Head discuss and agree on the draft Village Regulation proposed by the BPD and or the Village Head; (2) The discussion of the draft Village Regulation shall be held by the BPD in the BPD deliberation; (3) The Draft Village Regulation proposed by the Village Head is discussed in advance in the BPD internal deliberation no later than 10 (ten) working days from the time the draft Village

Function Implementation of Village Consultative Agency in Sendangan Satu Sonder District Minahasa Regency

Regulation is received by the BPD; (4) The implementation of the discussion of the draft Village Regulation between the BPD and the Village Head for the first time is carried out no later than 30 (thirty) days from the implementation of the BPD internal deliberation; (5) Every discussion of the draft Village Regulation shall be recorded in the process as outlined in the minutes of the deliberation.

Article 34 explains about Accommodating Community Aspirations, namely (1) Implementation of activities to accommodate community aspirations is carried out at the BPD secretariat; (2) The aspirations of the community are administered and conveyed in the BPD deliberation. Article 36 concerning Distribution of Community Aspirations (1) BPD shall channel the aspirations of the community in oral and or written form; (2) The distribution of community aspirations in the oral form such as the submission of community aspirations by the BPD in the BPD deliberation which is attended by the Village Head; (3) The distribution of community aspirations in writing, such as submitting aspirations through letters in the context of submitting input for the administration of the Village Government, requesting information to the Village Head, or submitting draft Village Regulations originating from the BPD proposal.

The implementation of Village Head Performance Supervision in Article 46, namely (1) BPD supervises the performance of the Village Head; (2) The implementation of supervision is carried out through a. Village Government activity planning; b. implementation of activities; and c. reporting on the implementation of Village Government; (3) The form of BPD supervision is in the form of monitoring and evaluation.

Based on this, if it is associated with the results of the research that the researchers have done, it can be explained that there are still many gaps between expectations and reality that the researchers have presented in the form of a table of findings starting from the first sub-focus or indicator, namely the Discussion and Agreement on Draft Village Regulations. in the village of Sendangan Satu, even more specifically, the BPD still does not know in detail the process of discussing and agreeing on the draft village regulation according to the policy, the second finding is that not all people have been invited to the village meeting, the draft village regulations that have been discussed and agreed to date have not yet become regulations. the village, then the implementors in the village of Sendangan Satu still do not understand in detail the period in the draft village regulation proposed by the village head.

In the indicator of accommodating and channelling the aspirations of the village community, there are several findings that the researchers got, namely related to the aspirations of the community that have been accommodated by the BPD but not all of the aspirations of the community have been heard, then there is a screening process for community aspirations carried out by the BPD, and the place where the distribution of community aspirations is not following regulation because it is still carried out flexibly, even the BPD and government officials do not know specifically the stages involved in the process of channelling people's aspirations. So this is very different from the operational theory which states that the implementation of activities to accommodate the aspirations of the community is carried out at the BPD secretariat which is then administered and delivered in the BPD deliberation. Furthermore, the BPD channel the aspirations of the community in oral and or written form.

Furthermore, on the indicators for the implementation of monitoring the performance of the village head, several findings were found, such as the BPD has carried out supervision of the performance of the village head but the supervision is not comprehensive, the process of implementing the supervision carried out by the BPD is still not properly known by the implementor, and the implementor has not understood it properly. related to the form of supervision that should be carried out by the BPD regarding the performance of the Village Head, while in theory it is explained that the Implementation of Monitoring the Performance of the Village Head starts from the BPD monitoring the performance of the Village Head, then the implementation of supervision is carried out through a) planning the activities of the Village Government; b) implementation of activities; and c) reporting on the implementation of Village Government, as well as the form of BPD supervision must be in the form of monitoring and evaluation.

Inhibiting Factors in the Implementation of the Functions of the Village Consultative Agency in Sendangan Satu Village, Sonder District, Minahasa Regency

To see the barriers to the effectiveness of a policy can be seen by using the public policy process model. There are so many models in the policy implementation process that can be used. namely starting from the policy implementation model proposed by Donald Van Mater and Carl Van Horn in Winarno, in which they suggested six variables that form the bond between policy and achievement of results and the importance of implementation procedures paying attention to the concepts of change, control and compliance. Among them are policy standards and targets to be achieved, resources, communication or quality of organizational reciprocity, characteristics of the agents involved in implementation, economic, social and political environment, and disposition or response of the implementor.

Policy implementation is a complex activity with so many factors that affect the success of policy implementation. In reviewing the implementation of public policies, Edwards III asks a basic question, namely what are the prerequisites for the implementation of a policy and what are the main factors inhibiting the success of policy implementation.

Akib discusses the Mazmanian and Sabatier policy implementation models which are classified into three general categories. The first category is the independent aspect concerning the ease or difficulty of controlling a problem. The scopes are 1) technical

Function Implementation of Village Consultative Agency in Sendangan Satu Sonder District Minahasa Regency

difficulties, 2) behavioural diversity of the target group, 3) the percentage of the target group compared to the total population, and 4) the scope of the desired behaviour change. The second category is the intervening aspect, namely the ability of the policy to systematize the policy implementation process or policy program management. The scopes are 1) clarity and consistency of policy objectives, 2) allocation of funding sources, 3) hierarchical integration within and between implementing agencies, 4) decision rules from implementing agencies, 5) recruitment of implementing officials, and 6) formal access to external parties. The third category is the dependent aspect, namely aspects outside the policy that affect the policy implementation process. The scopes are: 1) socio-economic and technological conditions, 2) public support, 3) group attitudes and resources, 4) support from superior officials, and 5) commitment and leadership ability to implement officials. While the bound aspects shown through the stages in the implementation process include: 1) implementing agency policy outputs, 2) the willingness of the target group to comply with policy outputs, 3) the real impact of policy outputs, 4) the perceived impact of policy outputs, and 5) improvements.

In every public policy, standards and objectives must always be clearly stated in each program because with clear standards and policy objectives, it will be easier to implement policies. On the other hand, there will often be failures caused by the lack of clarity about the standards and objectives of the policy. Determination of standards and objectives, one of which can use a statement from policymakers such as through a regulation, program guidelines and evaluation criteria for a policy.

For a public policy to be implemented effectively, the standards and objectives must be communicated to the implementers. This communication must be consistent and uniform (consistency and uniformity) from various sources of information. If there is no clarity and uniformity towards a standard and the objectives of a policy, it will be difficult to achieve the objectives of the policy. If different communication sources provide inconsistent (inconsistent) against a standard and objectives or sources of information provide conflicting interpretations (conflicting) then the policy will be difficult to implement intensively. The prospect of effective policy implementation is largely determined by the clarity of policy standards and objectives that are communicated to policy implementers accurately and consistently.

Disposition in policy implementation is defined as a tendency, desire or agreement of the implementers (implementors). To implement a policy, if it is to succeed effectively and efficiently, implementers not only know what to do and have the ability to implement the policy, but they must also have the will to implement the policy. However, how the implementers exercise their discretion depends on their inclination towards a policy. Then their attitude will be influenced by their views on a policy and the way they see the influence of the policy on the interests of their organization and their interests.

From the explanation above, if it is associated with the results of interviews that researchers have conducted, there are several findings obtained in this study, namely on the Standard and Objective indicators, it was found that the implementors still did not know the regulations related to the Village Consultative Agency (BPD), then the officials the existing government still does not understand in detail the functions of the BPD, in fact, it turns out that the Draft Village Regulations that have been produced to date have not been stipulated as Village Regulations and also until now there has been no technical guidance regarding the functions of the BPD from the village, sub-district or district governments. Meanwhile, in every public policy, standards and objectives must always be clearly stated in each program because with clear standards and policy objectives, it will be easier to implement policies.

In the communication indicator, it was found that the gap between expectations and reality started from rejection from the community regarding the draft village regulations that had been produced and there was an indifferent attitude regarding input given by the community to the Village Government and BPD, there was even socialization given to the leaders and members of the BPD. related to regulations governing BPD but not yet optimal, but there are good things where coordination between BPD and village government has gone well, even though according to this communication theory it must be consistent and uniform (consistency and uniformity) from various sources of information. If there is no clarity and uniformity towards a standard and the objectives of a policy, it will be difficult to achieve the objectives of the policy.

Furthermore, on the Implementing Disposition indicator, there are several findings, namely the attitude of the BPD in discussing and agreeing on the draft village regulation together with the village government that has been conveyed properly, the BPD and the Village Government have not been too transparent in conveying the Draft Village Regulation that has been produced to the community, and evaluation What has been done by the BPD on the performance of the village head is still carried out in oral form not in writing so that it is still not effective and efficient, while according to van meter and van horn explained that to implement policies if they want to succeed effectively and efficiently, the implementers do not only know what to do. carried out and have the ability to carry out the policy but they must also have the will to implement the policy.

If juxtaposed with previous research, it can be explained that there are differences, namely previous studies have different research loci where the researchers took the locus in Sendangan Satu Village, Sonder District, Minahasa Regency, while previous research took the locus in Bolangitang Satu Village, Bolangitang Barat District, North Bolangangmongondow Regency and Gentung Village, Pangkep Regency, but also have similarities, namely using qualitative research methods that emphasize more on meaning and both discuss the function of the Village Consultative Agency (BPD).

Function Implementation of Village Consultative Agency in Sendangan Satu Sonder District Minahasa Regency

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Implementation of the Functions of the Village Consultative Agency in Sendangan Satu Village, Sonder District, Minahasa Regency

Based on the results of the research data as described, analyzed, and the discussion of the results of the research data described in the previous chapter, in general, the BPD implementation has been implemented but several things have not been implemented properly, including:

1. Implementors in the village of Sendangan Satu still have not explored in detail the process of discussing and agreeing on the draft village regulation according to the policy.
2. The draft village regulations that have been discussed and agreed to date have not yet been established as village regulations.
3. The community's aspirations have been accommodated by the BPD but not all of the community's aspirations have been heard.
4. The place of implementation of the distribution of public aspirations is not following regulations because it is still carried out flexibly.
5. BPD and Government Officials do not know specifically the stages in the process of channelling public aspirations.
6. The supervision carried out by the BPD on the performance of the Village Head has not been thoroughly implemented.

Inhibiting Factors in the Implementation of the Functions of the Village Consultative Agency in Sendangan Satu Village, Sonder District, Minahasa Regency

Based on the results of research data as has been analyzed and discussion of research results that have been described in the previous chapter. So several conclusions are stated related to this research, namely:

1. The implementors still do not know clearly the regulations related to the Village Consultative Agency (BPD) and the functions of the BPD and even now there are no technical instructions regarding the functions of the BPD from the village, sub-district or district government.
2. There is rejection from the community regarding the draft village regulations that have been produced and there is an indifferent attitude regarding the input given by the community to the Village Government and BPD.
3. Socialization given to the leadership and members of BPD related to regulations governing BPD but not yet optimal.
4. The BPD and the Village Government have not been too transparent in conveying the Draft Village Regulations that have been produced to the Community.
5. The evaluation carried out by the BPD on the performance of the village head is still carried out in oral form not in writing so that it is still not effective and efficient.

V. SUGGESTION

1. Implementors must understand in detail the process of discussing and agreeing on draft regulations following regulations.
2. The village regulation draft must be immediately stipulated as a Village Regulation by the implementors so that this policy can run properly and correctly.
3. Supervision of the Village Head's Performance should be further improved.
4. Knowledge of regulations related to BPD should be optimized.
5. The entire submission of the Draft Village Regulation to the community must be carried out transparently.
6. The form of evaluation conducted by the BPD on the performance of the Village Head must also be in written form.
7. Approach by establishing communication and must be transparent.
8. From the results of research that has been carried out, if further research is related to policies governing BPD and it is necessary to carry out more in-depth research or similar research or with a different emphasis on focus, then you can also research other places or with a wider locus such as at the centre. to contribute scientific thinking in the development of public policy studies.

REFERENCES

- 1) Akib, H. (2012). Implementasi Kebijakan: Apa, Mengapa dan Bagaimana. *Ilmu Administrasi Publik*, 1–11.
- 2) Chandler, R. C., & Plano, J. C. (1988). *The Public Administration*. (Dictionary).
- 3) Easton, D. (1988). *Kerangka Kerja Analisa Sistem Politik*. (S. Simamora (ed.)). Jakarta: Bina Aksara.
- 4) Frederickson, H. G. (1997). *The Spirit of Public Administration*. Jossey-Bass Inc. Publishers.
- 5) Furchan, A. (1992). *Pengantar Metode Penelitian Kualitatif*. Usaha Nasional.
- 6) Indiahono, D. (2009). *Kebijakan Public Berbasis Dynamic Policy Analysis*. Gava Media.
- 7) Islamy, I. (1984). *Prinsip-prinsip perumusan kebijakan negara*. Bina Aksara.
- 8) Peraturan Menteri Dalam Negeri tentang Badan Permusyawaratan Desa, Pub. L. No. 10 (2016).
http://binapemdes.kemendagri.go.id/uploads/gallery/PERMENDAGRI_NO_110_THN_2016_TTG_BPD.pdf
- 9) Lincoln, Y. S., & Guba, E. G. (1985). *Naturalistic Inquiry*. California: Sage.
- 10) Lubis. (2007). *Metode Riset untuk Desain. Komunikasi Visual*. C.V Andi Offset.
- 11) Lumingkewas, L. (2006). *Pengantar Analisis Kebijakan Publik*. Wineka Media.

Function Implementation of Village Consultative Agency in Sendangan Satu Sonder District Minahasa Regency

- 12) Masuara, R. (2014). Pelaksanaan Fungsi Badan Permusyawaratan Desa (BPD) dalam Penyelenggaraan Pemerintahan Desa (Suatu Studi di Desa Bolangitang Satu Kecamatan Bolangitang Barat Kabupaten Bolaang Mongondow Utara). *Jurnal Politico*, 3((1)).
- 13) Miles, B. M., & Huberman, M. (1992). *Analisis Data Kualitatif Buku Sumber Tentang Metode-metode Baru*. UIP.
- 14) Moleong, L. J. (1994). *Penelitian Kualitatif*. PT Remaja. Rosdakarya.
- 15) Nugroho, R. (2011). *Public Policy: Dinamika Kebijakan, Analisis Kebijakan, Manajemen Kebijakan*. Elex Media Komputindo.
- 16) Pangkey, I., & Sendouw, R. (2020). Interconnection of Prime Service on Organization's Public Sector: A Study on Department of Demography and Civil Record of Manado City's Government North Sulawesi Province. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(03), 2128–2133. <https://doi.org/10.37200/ijpr/v24i3/pr200960>
- 17) Undang-undang (UU) tentang Desa, Pub. L. No. 6 (2014). <https://peraturan.bpk.go.id/Home/Download/27840/UU-Nomor-06-Tahun-2014.pdf>
- 18) Polii, E. H. (2021). Evaluation of Governance Implementation Minahasa Regency Drinking Water Company. *International Journal of Social Science and Human Research*, 04(06). <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijsshr/v4-i6-25>
- 19) Tangkilisan, H. S. (2007). *Manajemen Otonomi Daerah*. Lukman Offset.
- 20) Tumbel, G. (2021). Kebijakan Pembangunan Berbasis Lingkungan di Kota Manado. *Jurnal Administro : Jurnal Kajian Kebijakan Dan Ilmu Administrasi Negara*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.53682/administro.v2i1.1678>
- 21) Winarno, B. (2002). *Teori dan proses kebijakan publik*. Media Pressindo.